

IN-SITU DETECTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN CFRP BY BOTH ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE MEASUREMENTS AND ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In order to promote the industrial development of CFRP, it is essential to have sufficient knowledge of their durability. Therefore, it is necessary to study the mechanical behaviour of these materials and more particularly the evolution of various types of damage which appear during loading.

The measurement of the variation of the electrical resistance, in connection with Acoustic Emission analysis, was an accurate technique for the detection and the identification of damage mechanisms.

The CFRP samples were subjected to post-buckling tests. The monitoring in-situ of electrical resistance variation and AE activity allowed the detection, at different stages, of various types of damage mechanisms (fibre fracture, debonding, delamination,...)

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) present high specific mechanical properties (performance vs weight ratio). Thus during the last decade, they have been increasingly used as parts of structures having essential mechanical functions, especially in aeronautical applications.

It is therefore imperative to detect, evaluate, and analyse the various types of damage propagation caused by both static or cyclic loads and by environmental effects.

Although traditional non-destructive techniques (Ultrasonics (A-SCAN or C-SCAN), X-ray radiography, Infrared thermography, Holographic interferometry, Eddy currents,...) enable the a-posteriori detection of damage at successive stages of the life of these materials, it seems more difficult to monitor in-situ the evolution of internal damage nucleation and growth, especially in CFRP (opaque materials).

Since carbon fibres are electrical conductors ($\rho = 2.10^{-5} \Omega.m$), the measurement of the electrical resistance variations appears to be a valuable technique for this purpose.

In the case of CFRP samples, conductivity is not isotropic but depends on the orientation of the carbon fibres.

The electrical conduction of (0°) unidirectional (UD) CFRP parallel to the fibres is essentially due to the current flow along the fibres. This can be modelled using the parallel resistance approach (Fig.1).

The resistance of the composite R, may be written as follows :

$$R = \frac{\rho_f L}{b d V_f} + R_c$$

Where ρ_f is the fibre resistivity, V_f the volume fraction of unbroken fibres, L the length between the electrodes, b and d specimen width and thickness respectively, and R_c the contact resistance between the sample and the electrodes.

Fibre fractures, as show in figure 1, will cause V_f to decrease hence suddenly increasing the sample electrical resistance R .

Very few recent works [1-4] have used electrical resistance measurements to detect fibre breakage in longitudinal unidirectional CFRP laminates caused by monotonic and cyclic loading under tensile condition configuration.

But, the conduction behaviour depends also on fibre-to-fibre contacts between neighbouring fibres (Epoxy matrix is electrically insulating : $\rho = 10^{13}$ to $10^{15} \Omega.m$).

Below some critical values of fibre volume fraction (V_f), there are insufficient fibre-to-fibre contact paths and conductivity is not sufficiently large. But with current V_f values in engineering composites (50-60%), contact between fibres is always achieved. In this case, electrical conduction occurs through continuous paths between carbon fibres along and between the plies of the laminates.

Figure 1. (A) Damage mechanisms (fibre breaks) and (B) its electrical analogue

In conclusion, the conductive paths are formed in a 3 dimensional volume (Fig.1 and 2) :

- * In the longitudinal direction (X), with the carbon fibre.
- * In the transverse direction (Y), by fibre-to-fibre contacts between neighbouring fibres.
- * In the thickness of the sample (Z), by the contact between the plies of the laminates.

Hence conductivity variations allow the detection of fibre fracture, but also, in some case, the detection of intraply matrix cracking, debonding and delamination by modifications in fibre-fibre or ply-ply conduction paths and gradual cutting of the resistive tracks.

Figure 2 illustrates how matrix cracks and delamination can cause changes to conductive paths in the Y and Z directions.

The variation of the electrical conductivity can be taken as an indicator of the evolution of various types of damage in CFRP laminates.

On the other hand, the Acoustic Emission (AE) technique is now used to detect and possibly to identify damage mechanisms in CFRP. This is achieved by analysis of AE parameters like the amplitude event, and, to a lesser degree, the energy and the event duration.

But the comparison between amplitude values found during different tests and with different samples is sometimes difficult. Besides, it is critical to achieve a relation between amplitudes and rupture mechanisms. In spite of this, several authors [5-9] agree that low amplitudes are correlated with matrix cracking, medium amplitudes with delamination and high amplitudes with fibre breakage.

Following these preliminary remarks, both monitoring of the variations of the electrical resistance and the Acoustic Emissions will allow the in-situ detection and the identification of various types of damage mechanisms.

Figure 2.(A) Various types of damage mechanisms and (B) its electrical analogue

MATERIALS

The materials used were carbon fibre/epoxy laminates. These materials are made from Toray High Resistance fibre (T300-6K) and Ciba-Geigy DGEBA/DDM resin. Manufacture was achieved through layering of unidirectional tapes (12 plies) with subsequent curing in the autoclave. The fibre volume contents (V_f) must be sufficient to obtain contact between fibres. In our case, V_f was in the region of 60 %.

The CFRP sample had a width of 10 mm, a length of 100 mm and a thickness of about 1.7 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

MECHANICAL SYSTEM

Three-point bending tests induce local stress concentration beneath the loading nose. This may promote premature failure on the compressive side of the sample. This type of failure has already been referred to by several authors [10-12]. This always results from a microbuckling of the fibre (kink band) due to the local stress concentration. Such tests do not constitute a characterisation (even in compression) of the material, because of the complex stress state in the failure zone on the compressive side of the sample [13-15].

To overcome the difficulties bound with the compressive effects of the loading nose, a new bending test method was used [13,16,17]. The test consists in applying an axial compression to a rectangular cross section sample. The specimen is gripped at each end and can accommodate the local deformation at each end by in-plane rotation. Axial compression induces Euler-buckling of the bar (at the critical load P_c). In a post-buckling configuration, the sample is submitted to a bending strain as shown on Figure 3 where the parameters P , L_0 , a , δ , α , θ and f are defined.

Figure 3. Post-buckling bending test

In order to secure a quasi-pure bending strain it is necessary that both the contributions of the shear strain and pure compression strain become negligible. For the strain range considered, this condition is fulfilled if span to depth ratio (L_0/h) is greater than 52.

The determination of the bending stress and strain requires both the load P (easily measured by means of a force transducer) and the deflection at midspan f . f was calculated from the knowledge of the measured longitudinal displacement δ .

Tests were performed in an air conditioned room ($T = 23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; $\text{RH} = 50 \pm 5 \%$). The span to depth ratio (L_0/h) was chosen to be greater than 52 in order to minimize shear stresses. Monotonic tests were realised with constant cross-head speed of 2 mm/min.

ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

Figure 4 shows the sketch of the assembly used for the measurement of the electrical resistance. A constant electric current of about 50mA was introduced into the specimen by electrical cables soldered to U-shape copper plates.

The value of current intensity is deliberately very low to avoid heating the specimen. Electrical contact between carbon fibres and the copper plates was ensured with a silver adhesive. To increase this contact and therefore allow better current transfer, locally, the specimen ends and side surfaces were polished (suppression of insulator epoxy matrix which are softer than carbon fibre).

Owing to the Ohm's law, the electrical resistance can be determined.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of system used to monitor in-situ the electrical resistance

ACOUSTIC EMISSION SYSTEM

Acoustic emissions signals were acquired and processed with an AE acquisition and analysing system LOCAN Jr of Physical Acoustics Corp.

The AE signals during test were detected by a piezo-electric sensor (type R15) attached to the sample by a silicon grease and an adhesive tape. Its operating frequency range is between 50 and 200 KHz, and its resonant frequency is 70 KHz. This transducer was particularly recommended to detect damage in CFRP.

The signals were amplified by a pre and a post-amplifier by a total gain of 70dB. The threshold of AE system is 45dB, therefore emissions with amplitude lower than 45 dB are not detected.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The observation of fibre fracture is not possible during a test (opaque materials) except when fibres split off the specimen surface. However, the variation in electrical resistance during monotonic loading is a valuable indicator of fibre fracture in UD laminate.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of load P , electrical resistance and cumulative AE event counts versus displacement δ .

Figure 5. Post-buckling test of a (0°) UD laminate, showing the load/displacement curve and dependent electrical resistance and cumulative AE event counts

- A: First fibre fracture.
- B: First fibre bundle fracture.
- C: Debonding and delamination.
- D: Fibre bundle fracture...

Failures are progressive. The composite is damaged gradually by failures of fibres (and/or bundles), followed by delaminations on the tensile side of the sample. Indeed, compressive failures obtained in three-point bending [18] were therefore artifacts that masked intrinsic behaviour. This led to the conclusion that under bending loading conditions, the weak point of carbon epoxy studied composites is not, as it is often said, the behaviour in compression but, on the contrary, the resistance in tension.

The first failures occur generally due to macroscopic defects of the sample. These are defects due to the cutting of the sample, or, sometimes, defects of fibre alignment on the tensile side. These first fibre fractures (Fig.6b) cause the first increase of electrical resistance (after about 3 mm displacement).

Then, the damage propagates both across the width and through the thickness of the sample. So, when fibre bundles break, only on the tensile side of the sample (Fig.6c), the electrical resistance increases suddenly.

Owing to this, each fibre bundle breakage occurs regularly (for an increase of displacement of about 1 mm) inducing a step-shaped increase in electrical resistance.

These fibre bundle fractures are indicated, but with a much lower resolution, on the load-displacement curve by several losses of stiffness.

When fibre bundles break, the load P suddenly decreases. The amplitude of this drop is directly proportional to the number of broken fibres on the tensile side. Indeed only fibres which remained undamaged allow the load transfer.

In the same way, as the current flows along the fibres, the electrical resistance increases in proportion to the number of broken fibres.

In both cases, the calculations allow the determination of the number of broken fibres for each fibre bundle breakage. Similar results are obtained if considering the loss of stiffness or the increase in electrical resistance (for example, the first fibre bundle fracture correspond to a decrease of useful thickness of about 10%).

Concerning the Acoustic Emission, it remains negligible during the entire phase of compression. Therefore, in this type of test (with $L/h > 52$), the stage of compression does not involve damage. Acoustic Emission activity appears near the end of the loading plateau (for about 6 mm of displacement), even if no macroscopic damages is detected. In this zone, the amplitude of events are low (one distribution is adjusted around 50dB).

For about 8 mm displacement, the AE activity increases rapidly, as does the electrical resistance. Equally the load P decrease suddenly (Fig.5). The amplitude of AE events are high (greater than 75dB). That corresponds to fibre bundle fracture.

After this, there is no significant increase in AE activity, but the electrical resistance increases. The loss of stiffness is continual, and the amplitude of AE events is medium (distribution is around 62dB) and event durations are high (longer events = 200 μ s).

We can conclude, in this case, that debonding and delamination appear.

All of these assumptions were confirmed by microscopic examination of tested samples. The macroscopic views of each specimen are presented in figure 6.

Figure 6. Evolution of damage of (0°) UD CFRP laminates subjected in post-buckling condition

CONCLUSION

The measurement of the electrical resistance and analysis of Acoustic Emission parameters provide accurate means to monitor the in situ evolution of damage nucleation and growth in CFRP laminates, particularly for internal damage.

This method enabled the detection as well as the identification of various damage mechanisms (fibre fracture, matrix crack, delamination...). These types of damage appeared at different stages (each stage corresponding to one type of damage mechanism), inside (0°) CFRP laminates subjected to post-buckling tests.

Currently, this technique is being developed in several ways :

* Materials and more particularly the orientation of fibres : UD transverse (90°) and (±45°) CFRP laminates were studied.

* Sollicitation : Creep tests in hygro-thermal conditions were undertaken.

This, will finally lead to the detection of various types of damage (fibre fracture, matrix crack, debonding, delamination...) in composite structures under in-service and real time conditions.

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